

TELEMETRY

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Trustworthy Tools for Cybersecurity Testing and Vulnerability Detection in IoT Ecosystems

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Key Facts

Duration: September 2023 – November 2026

EU Contribution: € 4.425.570,00

Programme: Horizon Europe Programme

The Consortium

Coordinator: Nokia

Partners: A collaborative consortium of leading experts from academia, research institutions, and innovative private companies across the ICT, telecoms, aviation, and manufacturing sectors. A dynamic and interdisciplinary consortium of 11 partners from 9 EU countries, bringing together research, industry, SMEs, and public bodies.

The Challenge

The rapid expansion of the Internet of Things (IoT) has created a complex ecosystem where security vulnerabilities can have widespread consequences. Ensuring the trustworthiness of connected devices—from hardware to software—is a critical challenge, as traditional testing methods often fail to address the full lifecycle of components and systems.

TELEMETRY's primary objective is to develop and validate novel, trustworthy tools and methodologies for testing and detecting security vulnerabilities in IoT devices and systems. The project aims to enhance the security and reliability of connected devices, networks, and services across multiple sectors.

The Mission

The project's mission is to support the creation and sustainability of resilient digital infrastructures through continuous vulnerability and risk analysis of IoT components and ecosystems. Its core approach is built on three pillars:

- **Holistic Testing Methodologies:** Developing trustworthy tools, techniques, and methodologies for cybersecurity testing at both the component and system level.
- **Hardware & Software Integration:** Combining software cybersecurity with security of hardware devices, including firmware, software, and Software Bill of Materials (SBOMs), and underlying communication protocols.
- **Real-World Validation:** Demonstrating advancements through three real-world use cases in aviation, smart manufacturing, and telecommunications.

The Impact

Novel Testing Toolkit

- **Trustworthy Tools:** Developing a suite of reliable tools for vulnerability detection and anomaly monitoring in running systems.
- **Methodologies for Complete Lifecycle:** Determining methodologies for using these tools individually, together, and alongside third-party tools to support the entire lifecycle of IoT components and systems.

Enhanced Security Across Sectors

- **Proactive Vulnerability Management:** Helping developers avoid security bugs and flaws, while enabling third parties to detect anomalies and prevent attacks in operational systems.
- **Sector-Specific Impact:** Delivering validated solutions for critical sectors:
- **Telecommunications:** Protecting sensitive data and ensuring reliability of increasingly IoT-dependent networks.
- **Aviation & Smart Manufacturing:** Demonstrating security advancements in complex, high-stakes environments.

Regulatory & Standards Alignment

- **Certification Support:** Ensuring tools and methodologies support compliance with relevant certification standards.
- **Knowledge Dissemination:** Sharing findings and best practices through publications, workshops, and recognition such as being selected as CORDIS Project of the Month.

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